

Figure S1. The phylogenetic tree with the 12 chitinase-encoding genes sequences of *Chitinibacter tainanensis* CT01 and the other chitinase genes sequences.

Figure S2. SDS-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis of chitinase 1198 from recombinant *E. coli*. M, molecular mass; Lane 1, cell lysate of *E. coli* before IPTG induction; Lane 2, cell lysate of *E. coli* after IPTG induction for 7 hours; Lane 3, supernatant; Lane 4, precipitation of *E. coli* lysate after sonication and centrifugation.

atgtgcactttaatcgttttgctgtagctgtattcctgctgactgatggccgtggccagcttctcttacgctgctgatgctggaagaaggt
M S H F N R F A V A A I P A A L M A V A S F S Y A A D A W K E G
tcgacctataacgcaggcactgtgtttcataatgccgtaacgactaccaagcctctggtagctcacactgccactgtggcgctaacggaaacct
S T Y N A G T V V S Y A G N D Y Q A L V T H T A Y V G A N W N P
gcttcaaccccaactgtggaactggttgctaccggttctgctacgccagcgaaccgcgacccagtaacaacggctaagccaaccagggc
A S T P T L W K L V A T G S A T P A P T A T P V T T A K P T T A
ccaacaactgcgccaaccaccgaccgacaactgctccaactaccgcgccaactactggcccagtagcaggttggctctgtagcggcttgaat
P T T A P T T A P T T A P T T A P T T G P V A G C G S V A A W N
tcaactgctgctatagcggcgagtagttgcc tacaacggcgcaaaactcagctaaatggtagacacaaggtcaggcgcttctgcaact
S T A A Y S G G A V V A Y N G G K Y S A K W W T Q G Q A P S A T
gatcagtggggcccatacgaagcgagtgccgcccagctgtaactgcgacccaactgtagcgaacaccaaccccagttggatgacc
D Q W G P W K Y E G E C G P A V T A T P T V A P T P T P V G M T
ccagaccaaccgtagcgaactccaactgcagttccaactgcagcgaacaccagttgctacctggctccaggtaagaagtgctccacct
P A P T V A P T P T A V P T A A P T P V A T L A P G Q E V P P P
gcgcaagcgaagttggctcttacttcaactcagtgggcgctgtatggctgtagctaccaagttgccacatcatctctagcggcgctgctcagcaa
A Q A Q V G S Y F T Q W G V Y G R D Y Q V A D I I S S G A A Q Q
ctgacctcatcaactacgcttccgtaacatctaccagaaaaatggtagctgagtgaggatcgtgaacaaactggaaccaggtgcaactgat
L T F I N Y A F G N I Y Q K N G G Y E C G I V N K L E P G A T D
gcaaatgcaccagcgctggtactggtggcgatgcttggccgacttggctgtagctgcaaacgctggttgaaccagctgatacaatcaagtg
A N A P G A G T G G D A W A D F G L T A K R R V D P A D Q I K W
gacgcaaaactggccgtaacttccgtgagttccaggcttataagaaaaatccccagacacaaactgttcatctctctgggtggctggacttgg
D D K L A G N F R E F Q A Y K K K F P D T K L F I S L G G W T W
tcgaaatggttctctgctgcatcgaaaaccgacgctgctgtaaacagctggttaaatcgtgtagctacatctacatcaaaggaacttgccagt
S K W F S A A S K T D A L R K Q L V K S C I D I Y I K G N L P V
gtggatggccgtggtggcgaggttcagctgcgaacatcttcgatggtatcgatcagctgggaatccccaggtgtcaaggcggtgggttacaac
V D G R G G A G S A A N I F D G I D I D W E F P G V Q G V G Y N
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T V A P E D K Q N F T L L L A E F R K Q L D E L A A A N Q K K Y
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Y L T V A I G V G R D K I E M T E P R E Y A R Y L D W I N M M T
tagctacaacggcggtggaacgcacaaggcccagctgacttccagctcactgttctgctgatcaagcaaccacagtaacgtgctctggc
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K P A D K C Y G D R S L V S Y Y N T D D A V N L L I Q A G V N P
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K K L V V G I P K Y G R G W T G V T N V N N G L Y Q K A T D A A
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R G T Y E K G I E D F K V L K N A A G T V Y V H P V T K Q S Y K
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F D G S T F W S Y D T P E V I Q T K I D Y A K A K G L N G G V F
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S W S L D G D D S A A T L S K A M G K A R Q K G E L N S K L E G
aagcctatcccataacctctctcgttctcgttctcagcgtaccggctcatcatcaccatcac
K P I P N P L L G L D S T R T G H H H H H

Figure S3 Amino acid and DNA sequence of chitinase 1198.

Figure S4. (A) Secondary structures of chitinase 1198. (B) Predicted 3D structures of chitinase 1198.

Figure S5. Multiple sequence alignment of the active site (green box: DXXDXDXE one letter amino acid motif) of the deduced protein sequence of chitinase 1198 with chitinase from Arthobacter (PDB ID: 1KFW), (PDB ID: 4W5U), Bacillus circulans (PDB ID: 1ITX), Serratia marcescens (PDB ID: 2WLY) and chitinase from nematophagous fungus (PDB ID: 3G6L).

Figure S6. Comparing the Chi1198 3D structures (colored in green) with chitinases. from *Arthobacter* (PDB ID: 1KFW and colored in purple), (PDB ID: 4W5U and colored in gray), *Bacillus circulans* (PDB ID: 1ITX and colored in cyan), *Serratia marcescens* (PDB ID: 2WLY and colored in tints) and chitinase from nematophagous fungus (PDB ID: 3G6L and colored in blue).

Figure S7. Chi1198 with chitin oligomers (repeat unit: 12) and Family 18 chitinase: DXXDXDXE amino acid motif. (The distance between the Asp440 of chitinase1198 and the nitrogen atom of the 2nd repeat unit from the nonreducing end)

Figure S8. Chi1198 with chitin oligomers (repeat unit: 12) and Family 18 chitinase: DXXDXDXE amino acid motif. (The distance between the Asp440 of chitinase1198 and the nitrogen atom of the 3rd repeat unit from the nonreducing end)

Figure S9. Chi1198 with chitin oligomers (repeat unit: 3) and Family 18 chitinase: DXXDXDXE amino acid motif. (The distance between the Asp440 of chitinase1198 and the nitrogen atom of the 2nd repeat unit from the nonreducing end)